

**PILOTs for robotic INSpection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

**Deliverable D9.4
Impact assessment report**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871542

Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	ICT-871542
Starting Date	January 1 st , 2020
Duration	48 months
Call Identifier	H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic	ICT-09-2019-2020 (B) (IA)
Project Website	www.piloting-project.eu
Project Manager	Antidio Viguria
Organisation	Fundación Andaluza para el Desarrollo Aeroespacial (CATEC)
E-mail	aviguria@catec.aero

Document Information

Due date: 31/12/2022	Submission date: 23/12/2022
Lead beneficiary: FERROVIAL	Version: 1.0
Work Package	9-Social, Ethical and Legal (SoEL) aspects
Deliverable Title	Impact assessment report
Main Editor(s)	FERROVIAL
Contributor(s)	CHEVRON, EGNATIA, APPLUS, INLECOM, CATEC
Reviewer (s)	CATEC

Document Classification					
Status	F	Nature	R	Dissemination level	PU
Draft: D Final: F		R = Report P = Prototype D = Demonstrator O = Other		PU = Public PP = Restricted to other programme participants* RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium * *including the Commission Services	

Revision history				
Version	Issue Date	Status	Autor(s)	
0.7	10.10.2022	First Draft	FERROVIAL	
0.8	8.11.2022	Partners Contribution	CHEVRON, EGNATIA, APPLUS, INLECOM, CATEC	
0.9	30.11.2022	First complete and revised version	CATEC	
1.0	9.12.2022	Reviewed version considering comments	version reviewer	FERROVIAL

Contents

1. Introduction	8
1.1 Purpose of the document.....	8
1.2 Scope of the document.....	8
1.3 Structure of the document.....	8
2. PILOTING impact assessment.....	9
2.1 SoEL impact assessment identification	10
2.1.1 Questionnaire relating to the PILOTING project social aspects: GDPR	11
2.1.2 Questionnaire relating to the PILOTING project ethical aspects: AI developments	14
2.1.3 Questionnaire relating to the PILOTING project legal aspects: UAV and UGV	16
regulations.	16
2.2 SoEL impact assessment analysis.....	20
2.3 SoEL impact assessment evaluation and treatment	21
2.4 Consultation of an external SoEL expert.....	30
3. Monitoring the correct execution of the project against the SoEL requirements.....	31
3.1 Monitoring that the results of the 1 st PILOTING impact assessment (D9.2) are being	31
implemented.....	31
3.2 How PILOTING complies with SoEL requirements.....	45
4. Conclusions	52
Annex I: Informed consent form (examples)	54

List of Figures

Figure 1. Impact Assessment Methodology 9

Figure 2. Privacy Notice include in the PILOTING User Group invitation e-mail. 33

Figure 3. Example of email to include the Informed consent form in this deliverable. 36

List of Tables

Table 1. List of acronyms.	6
Table 2. List of PILOTING I&M actors who have participated in the SoEL Impact Assessment Identification questionnaires.....	10
Table 3. Risk matrix.	21
Table 4. PILOTING SoEL identified risks and evaluation.	22
Table 5. Management risks identified in the 1 st Impact Assessment Report (D9.2) – Update.	32
Table 6. Technical risks identified in the 1 st Impact Assessment Report (D9.2) – Update.....	38
Table 7. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Scenario.....	45

Acronyms

Table 1. List of acronyms.

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ATEX	ATmosphères EXplosives (French for "Explosive Atmospheres") - Common name for Directive 2014/34/EU
BVLOS	Beyond Visual Line Of Sight
CE	Conformité Européenne (French for "European Conformity")
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
EU	European Union
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GM	General Meeting
HQ	Headquarters
HW	Hardware
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
IA	Innovation Action
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEC	Industrial Executive Committee
IECEX	International Electrotechnical Commission System for Certification to Standards Relating to Equipment for Use in Explosive Atmospheres
IR	Infrared Camera
IRM	Information Risk Management
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LNE	Laboratoire national de métrologie et d'essais (French for "National Laboratory of Metrology and Testing")
LVD	Low Voltage Directive
N/A	Not Applicable
NDE	Non-Destructive Examination
NL	Netherlands
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
R&D	Research and Development
RoHS	Restriction of Hazardous Substance

RPAS	Remotely Piloted Aircraft System
RVIS	Remote Visual Inspection Services
SoEL	Social, Ethical, and Legal
SW	Software
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft System
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
USA	United States of America
VLOS	Visual Line Of Sight
WEEE	Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document presents an assessment related to the societal, ethical and legal aspects (described within D9.3) that could affect the PILOTING technological developments and their future exploitation. This SoEL assessment is composed of three steps: identification, analysis and evaluation/treatment. The identification step has been performed using questionnaires and gathering answers from PILOTING end-users and consultation with an external SoEL expert. After analysis of the different inputs, several SoEL related risks have been identified. Then, a contingency plan has been defined per risk. This analysis and contingency plans have been presented, updated and agreed with PILOTING IEC (Industrial Executive Committee).

On the other hand, this deliverable also reviewed the original SoEL risks (defined in D9.2) focused on the activities to be developed during the project. Then, it is described how the project consortium has applied the different contingency plans defined for the different SoEL risks. Moreover, this deliverable also explains how the consortium have fulfilled the identified SoEL aspects when executing the PILOTING pilot experiments.

1.2 Scope of the document

The primary aim of the PILOTING impact assessment is to assess the potential impacts of applying the requirements of the social, ethical and legal aspects identified within Task T9.1 "Identification of SoEL background requirements" (covered in deliverables D9.1 and D9.3) to the PILOTING technological developments. This SoEL impact assessment is performed as part of the WP9 activities.

In months M6 and M12 of the project, the first version of the deliverables, D9.1 "Principles for impact assessment of PILOTING against SoEL requirements" and D9.2 "Impact assessment report" were developed. Now, in this second period of the project, when the PILOTING developments have achieved a higher level of maturity and the regulation related to the novel technologies being developed within the project has suffered updates, a new version of these deliverables has been completed.

This deliverable covers how the PILOTING platform and technologies are impacted by the SoEL requirements identified in the D9.3, and it presents how the results of the 1st impact assessment report (D9.2) are being implemented by all relevant partners as the developed systems are integrated, tested and evaluated in the pilot experiments.

1.3 Structure of the document

The Impact assessment report has the following sections:

- Section 1 describes the purpose, scope, and structure of the deliverable.

- Section 2 details the SoEL Impact assessment addressed by PILOTING, and how the possible risk of non-compliance with the SoEL requirements will be: 1) identified using questionnaires and meetings with end-users; 2) analysed, and 3) evaluated and treated in order to avoid or minimize the possible negative consequences and impacts.
- Section 3 summarizes how the PILOTING consortium is monitoring that the results of the 1st "Impact Assessment Report" (D9.2) are being implemented (both at the execution of project activities and also the pilot experiments).
- Section 4 presents the conclusions of this deliverable.

2. PILOTING impact assessment

As was just mentioned, the methodology followed in this 2nd "Impact Assessment Report" is the same as the one already defined in D9.1 and it is based on three steps (see Figure 1):

1. Impact assessment identification: to help the identification of possible risks related with non-compliance with SoEL requirements. To perform this assessment, PILOTING consortium has used questionnaires, meetings with partners (including a PILOTING IEC meeting) and a collaboration established with the [Robotics4EU](#)¹ Project. This collaboration has been focused on obtaining feedback to complete the Impact Assessment section based on a professional point of view to establish and evaluate the SoEL requirements related to PILOTING technologies.
2. Impact assessment analysis: the quantification and qualification will be performed during the analysis of the identified risks.
3. Impact assessment evaluation and treatment: A contingency plan will be defined to avoid/minimize each identified risk.

Figure 1. Impact Assessment Methodology

¹ [Robotics4EU Project](#)

2.1 SoEL impact assessment identification

The 1st "Impact Assessment Report" (D9.1), detailed the approach of the PILOTING project consortium to the SoEL Impact assessment, through a series of questionnaires based on the PILOTING activity which were distributed among the PILOTING partners.

However, in this second version, the questionnaires will be addressed to PILOTING end-users in order to get feedback about the main risks that they envision in the use of these new robotics technologies within the I&M sector. The result will be a new version of the risk of non-compliance with SoEL requirements, more focused on the future exploitation of the PILOTING technologies, which complements the results obtained in the 1st "Impact assessment report" (D9.2), more focused on test the compliance with the SoEL requirements during the development of the PILOTING R&D project.

In this 2nd "Impact assessment report", the questionnaires have been structured in the following areas:

- Requirements related to the **PILOTING project social aspects**: personal **data protection**, ethical principles, and privacy.
- Requirements related to the **PILOTING project ethical aspects**: **AI developments**.
- Requirements related to **PILOTING project legal aspects**: **UAV and UGV regulations**.

The questions included in these questionnaires have been chosen by PILOTING consortium, in order to ensure compliance with all the applicable SoEL requirements, defined in the Guidelines for the impact assessment (see deliverable D9.3). Apart from the questionnaire, also meetings with PILOTING partners have been held to support the risk identification process, including a meeting of the PILOTING IEC on December 1st, 2022.

Table 2 shows who have participated in answering the questionnaires, not giving the name for privacy reasons.

Table 2. List of PILOTING I&M actors who have participated in the SoEL Impact Assessment Identification questionnaires.

Organization	Role	ID
CHEVRON	Senior inspection / materials engineers in CHEVRON's Robotics group who are not directly involved in PILOTING.	User 1
CHEVRON	Senior inspection / materials engineers in CHEVRON's Robotics group who are not directly involved in PILOTING.	User 2
CHEVRON	Senior inspection / materials engineers in CHEVRON's Robotics group who are not directly involved in PILOTING.	User 3
FERROVIAL	FERROVIAL's drone expert + FERROVIAL's innovation project manager	User 4
EGNATIA ODOS	EGNATIA's inspection expert	User 5
APPLUS	APPLUS's senior inspection manager	User 6

2.1.1 Questionnaire relating to the PILOTING project social aspects: GDPR

- 1. Do you know what is GDPR?**
 - **User 1 (CHEVRON):** No.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** No.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** Yes.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** Yes.

- 2. Do you have experience in applying the GDPR regulation to inspection tasks? If yes, please, briefly specify this experience.**
 - **User 1 (CHEVRON):** No.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Not Known.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes, FERROVIAL has a lot of GDPR internal regulatory.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No for tunnel inspections.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** No.

- 3. Do you know if GDPR applies to the inspection activities that your company is already developing?**
 - **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No as tunnel environment is totally isolated from irrelevant people.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** Yes.

- 4. Do you have a department or person in your company in charge of verifying compliance with GDPR regulation of the different inspection activities that are developed in your company?**
 - **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not known. Chevron has an Information Risk Management (IRM) department that deals with general Data Privacy (not specific to inspection activities). Each Business Unit has a corresponding Data Protection Officer.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes, but doesn't know the name.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** Yes, the IT department is in charge.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** Yes, Mrs. Elena Hoekstra, Legal Counsel. Based in the Netherlands

5. **If so, do you know if you already have a designated DPO (Data Protection Officer) in your company?**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Yes.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Yes, we have a group dedicated to this.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Not known.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** Yes.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** Yes, Mr. Mario Alonso, Senior Legal Counsel.
6. **During the inspection and maintenance procedures, do you think it could be possible that there are non-involved people in the vicinity to the personnel who carry out the inspection works? If yes, please, specify.**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Yes. Given that routine inspections often occur while equipment is in operation, it is very likely that other functions (operators, engineers, mechanics) could be in the same vicinity while inspection activities are being performed.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** No.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No. Inside the tunnels there are not people present, irrelevant to maintenance and inspection activities.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** No.
7. **Do you know if there are defined informed consent procedures in your company for inspection activities that could involve people not directly related with the inspection task? If yes, please, briefly specify them.**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not Know. Chevron has defined procedures for personal image / photo releases for public affair activities. I am not aware of similar procedures for inspection activities. For inspection activities that involve hazards (example: radiography), Chevron has procedures for quarantining areas to ensure people not directly related with inspection activities are not exposed to inspection-related hazards.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Yes, with a legitimate purpose.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes, it depends on the type of work sites. Non commonly used for viaducts inspection.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No, as there is no need for inspection inside motorway tunnels.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** No, not applicable.
8. **If the use of robotic vehicles in inspection tasks would imply the implementation of informed consent procedures in case non-involved people are around, do you see feasible to apply these types of procedures by the people that directly perform the inspections?**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Yes, with assistance from operations.

- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** The robotic operators are considered part of the inspection crew. Other people can participate when justified.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Yes.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No, Viaducts zones are owned by Statal company, all photos taken there need to be approved only by this company.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** Yes.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** If applicable yes, feasible. But not applicable here.

9. Do you think there is a possibility of processing personal sensitive data during the inspection activities that your company usually performs?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** No (low likelihood that personal sensitive data will be captured as part of the inspection activities).
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Processing of data is done by the Inspection Company and returned to Chevron. Required contracts and NDA's will be needed to share with others.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes, but it implies more inspection timing.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No in tunnel inspections.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** No.

10. In the I&M activities that your company is currently performing, are images, taken during the inspection, stored in the company's database? For how long?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Yes. Image / data retention duration must comply with Chevron data retention policies and can vary from 3-years to indefinitely (if considered permanent records).
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** We have no limit for storage, in principle we will save data as needed.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not Known.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes, only selected photos are stored, but time doesn't know. Currently those contracts are not in Europe.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** Yes.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** Yes. Object images are stored for an undefined period of time.

11. Who has access to the data collected during these inspections? For how long? Could you please briefly describe the access rules (for example describing the main roles in the company that has access to these images)?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):**
 - Local Chevron facility inspectors generally have access to the data collected during inspection activities. Data can be shared with other local Chevron facility functions (engineers, ops management, maintenance) as well as global Chevron personnel (technical SME's) as deemed appropriate.
 - Data retention duration depends on the type of data and can range from 3-years to indefinitely.

- Data accessibility is generally managed site-by-site for data stored on-prem. However, as more data is moved to cloud storage, data collectors have initial responsibility for assigning data sensitivity as part of the metadata which then governs data accessibility.
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Chevron personnel with privilege to access that information.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not Known.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Only specific technician, and local authorities if it is required. After GDPR is applied to those photos, many people of the organization can have access to those photos.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** The structures inspection/maintenance and assessment manager of our company has only access in the collected data as well as IT Dept charged with GDPR.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** Data is stored at company's cloud storage, only accessible if access has been specifically granted.
Current hierarchy access: the creator (inspector), management & IT
Creator, APPLUS RVIS management & IT: edit, read & write.

2.1.2 Questionnaire relating to the PILOTING project ethical aspects: AI developments

- 12. Do you know if your company currently applies AI solutions to the inspection processes? If yes, please, specify.**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not currently, but several development efforts are occurring in the AI space. The two biggest obstacles towards AI adoption appear to be 1) amount of training data available and 2) a consistent framework for evaluating the AI accuracy relative to current human inspection processes.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** No, we are not using AI for inspection or NDE purposes.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes, no more info available.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** No.
- 13. If yes, do you know if your company had any problems, in terms of societal or ethical issues, integrating AI solutions into your company's inspection processes? If yes, please, specify.**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** No.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** N/A.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** No.
- 14. Are you aware of any specific regulation or European Commission guidelines that the implemented AI-based algorithms should fulfil? If yes, please, specify which ones.**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** No.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** No.

- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No, countries with which we work are non-European.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** No.

15. If apply, do you know whether the current AI-based solutions in your company comply with these regulations or EC guidelines?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
- **User 2(CHEVRON):** Not known.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Not known.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** N/A.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** Not applicable.

16. Do you have personal experience in applying any type of regulation from a social and ethical point of view to AI algorithms? If yes, please, specify.

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 2(CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes, in Defense field, underwater mine inspection.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** No, but if such projects are being initiated, we will follow legal counselling first before.

17. Does your company have a department or person in charge of verifying compliance of applied AI algorithms with latest regulation or guidelines from a social and ethical point of view?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Not known.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** Legal department, lead in Spain HQ.

18. Do you think that AI algorithms applied to inspection tasks will have in the future to comply with AI-based regulation from an ethical or societal point of view? If yes, please, specify.

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** No. My current Point-of-View is that regulations / guidelines will primarily pertain to the requirements behind validating the effectiveness of AI solutions before they are fully implemented. I cannot think of any ethical or societal AI-based regulations at this point in time.
- **User 2(CHEVRON):** No.

- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes, will be under regulation in order to meet the legal requirement.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** We are, at this point, not aware of any implications that might involve ethical or societal issues.

19. Do you think if AI-based algorithms applied to inspection tasks could integrate any type of bias that could be problematic from an ethical or societal point of view or due to the nature of the inspection tasks this will most probably not apply?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** No, we will use AI as a guideline, there are no plans to fully replace people for the final decision.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** Highly unlikely to my knowledge since inspection results should only involve matter and object-based algorithms.

20. Are you aware of any specific requirement, regulation or standard that AI algorithms have to fulfil before using it in your company?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** No. However, Chevron is trying to develop framework for consistently defining & applying requirements for evaluating AI solutions prior to scaling (for computer vision / image recognition type AI).
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** No, not applicable since we are currently not practicing any activities related to AI within APPLUS RVIS.

2.1.3 Questionnaire relating to the PILOTING project legal aspects: UAV and UGV regulations.

2.1.3.1 UAV regulation

21. Within your company, is there any previous experience in using UAVs for any inspection application?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Yes.
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Yes.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Yes.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** Yes.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** Yes.

- 22. If yes, do you know which category of UAS operations (open or specific) apply?**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Both of them.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Don't know the definition of Open or Specific.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Only open category.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** Only open category.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** Only specific category, RPAS under 25 kg.
- 23. Do you know if your company has a department or person in charge of verifying compliance with UAV regulation? If yes, please, specify.**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Yes. Chevron Aviation Services.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Yes.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** Yes, APPLUS Australia.
- 24. Do you know if your company has encountered any relevant problem/bottleneck in being complaint with the European Drone Regulation? If yes, please, specify.**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not known. Currently, all Chevron UAS operations within the EU are conducted by third party service providers.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Don't know.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** Yes. Regulation restrictions was the main reason why APPLUS RVIS in the Netherlands terminated drone services.
- 25. Specific category: If your company flights are performed in this category of operation, do you know if your company has a person in charge of managing flight permissions or it is outsourced? If yes, please, specify.**
- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Don't know the definition of Specific Category.
 - **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
 - **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No.
 - **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No license is needed for flying inside isolated drainage tunnels or under tall ravine bridges in mountain.
 - **User 6 (APPLUS):** Not applicable from our NL offices anymore.

26. Specific category: If your company flights are performed in this category of operation and if your company is taking care of managing the flight permissions, do you know which are the major difficulties they are facing?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Don't know the definition of Specific Category.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** N/A.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** N/A.

27. Are you aware of any specific requirement, regulation or standard that UAVs (apart from the European Drone Regulation) have to fulfil before using it in your company?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Yes, FAA Part 107 for sUAS operations in USA, CASA sUAS, regulations for Australian sUAS operations, Other Regional Civilian Aviation Authority Regulations, Chevron Aviation Services Aviation Manual
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Yes, FAA-Part 107, plus internal requirements.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** No.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes, we are aware about the existence but still doesn't need.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** No longer applicable for APPLUS RVIS NL.

2.1.3.2 UGV regulation

28. Within your company, is there any previous experience in using UGV for any inspection or maintenance application?

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Yes.
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Yes.
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Yes.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** Yes.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** No.

29. Do you know if your company has a department or person in charge of verifying compliance with any type of UGV-related regulation or guidelines? If yes, please, specify.

- **User 1 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
- **User 2 (CHEVRON):** Yes, Explosive Area Certification
- **User 3 (CHEVRON):** Not known.
- **User 4 (FERROVIAL):** No.
- **User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS):** No.
- **User 6 (APPLUS):** No.

- 30. Are you aware of any specific regulation or European Commission guidelines that UGVs should fulfil? If yes, please, specify which ones.**
- User 1 (CHEVRON): No.
 - User 2 (CHEVRON): No.
 - User 3 (CHEVRON): No.
 - User 4 (FERROVIAL): No.
 - User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS): No.
 - User 6 (APPLUS): No.
- 31. If yes, do you know if your company currently complies with any guidelines/regulations for the operation of UGVs? If yes, could you briefly describe them?**
- User 1 (CHEVRON): Not known.
 - User 2 (CHEVRON): API-500/505 For explosive areas; ATEX, IECEx where needed.
 - User 3 (CHEVRON): Not known.
 - User 4 (FERROVIAL): Not known.
 - User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS): N/A.
 - User 6 (APPLUS): Not known.
- 32. Do you know if your company has encountered any problems/bottleneck relevant to the implementation of any relevant guidelines/regulation to UGVs for inspection applications? If yes, please, specify.**
- User 1 (CHEVRON): Not known.
 - User 2 (CHEVRON): No.
 - User 3 (CHEVRON): Not known.
 - User 4 (FERROVIAL): No.
 - User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS): N/A.
 - User 6 (APPLUS): Not known
- 33. Are you aware of any specific requirement, regulation or standard that UGVs (apart from the European Drone Regulation) have to fulfil before using it in your company?**
- User 1 (CHEVRON): Yes, ATEX certification for operation in explosive or potentially explosive environments.
 - User 2 (CHEVRON): Yes. Explosive Area Certifications.
 - User 3 (CHEVRON): No.
 - User 4 (FERROVIAL): No.
 - User 5 (EGNATIA ODOS): No.
 - User 6 (APPLUS): No.

2.2 SoEL impact assessment analysis

The procedure to complete the SoEL Impact Assessment Analysis will be the same that in the D9.2. In this section, this methodology is reminded as well as the analysis of potential risks of non-compliance with the SoEL requirements identified.

For PILOTING project, a risk is defined as an event, which could potentially have an adverse effect on a team's progress and success. Any risk has a severity of the impact (or consequences) and a probability (or likelihood) of occurrence. The quantification and qualification of risk is based in these two dimensions. In order to have a proper analysis of the risk and of course to be able to prioritize when it comes to the planning of responses both probability and impact of a risk needs to be defined.

Risk **probability**, or likelihood, is the possibility of a risk event occurring. Probability of risk to occur can be mapped to one of the following three-grade scale:

- Low- In similar activities, few or no occurrences of the risk happened, thus risk can be handled reliably. Risk shall be periodically monitored and high-level action plan in case risk occurs should be elaborated upon. Depending on the nature or root cause, a set of preventative or mitigation actions should be identified.
- Medium - Risks of similar nature have happened rarely in other similar activities and the current situation has few assumptions that are somewhat favourable to the emergence of the risk. A detailed action plan should be developed in case of the event occur. Depending on the nature or root cause, set of avoidance or mitigation actions should be assessed and broken down into steps.
- High- There is a significantly high chance that the risk will occur. Major trade-offs between SoEL requirements and PILOTING functionalities should be thoroughly discussed and a set of avoidance or mitigation actions (depending on the nature or root cause) should be ready for implementation.

Impacts are often defined as the consequences, or effects of a risk event on the project objectives. A five-grade scale is detailed as follows:

- Low- If the risk occurs, it does not threaten the rights and freedoms of the individual or causes necessity of only minor or no modification or adaptation of the project. Limitation of the SoEL requirements remains lawful, necessary, and proportionate.
- Medium- If the risk occurs, it can be deemed as a threat to the rights and freedoms of the individual. Several elements in the system should be revised and/or modified (however staying on an acceptable level).
- High- If the risk occurs, rights and freedoms of the individual are highly affected, thus one or more goals of the project will not be met. Significant revision and re-orientation (i.e., technical) is needed.

The risk rating is the overall effect of a risk happening. For PILOTING, risk ratings of Low, Medium, or High are assigned based on the following risk matrix:

Table 3. Risk matrix.

Probability/Impact	Low	Medium	High
High	Medium	High	High
Medium	Low	Medium	High
Low	Low	Low	Medium

These categories can help the consortium prioritize between risks and decide which risks should be mitigated or avoided first and which should leave space for other treatment options. The answers provided to the questionnaire contain information to identify, assess, and categorize the probability and impact of risks against SoEL requirements. For PILOTING, risk ratings of Low, Medium, or High imply:

- Low, if Very Unlikely or Unlikely to occur,
- Medium, if Possible to occur,
- High, if Likely or Almost Certain

Table 4 shows the analysis of the risks identified on this 2nd PILOTING SoEL Impact Assessment.

2.3 SoEL impact assessment evaluation and treatment

After the project's risks have been identified and assessed, the approach to handle each significant risk must be developed. There are essentially four techniques or options for handling risks:

- **Avoid:** when you avoid the risk, it means you change your plan to eliminate the probability of the risk, or the effect of the risk, if it does occur.
- **Transfer:** risk transference occurs when the negative impact is shifted to a third party, such as through an insurance policy or penalty clause in a contract. The risk may still occur however the financial impact will be somewhat displaced. Risk transference usually involves some type of contractual agreement.
- **Mitigate:** risk mitigation occurs when you proactively change the plan to minimize the impact or probability of the risk occurring. Risk mitigation does not eliminate the risk and as such there will be some residual risk remaining.
- **Accept:** there are few risks which are out of control of project organization and project manager has no other option but to accept them and still continue running the project by finding alternate ways to tackle the issues arising from these risks. For all identified risks, the various handling techniques should be evaluated in terms of feasibility, expected effectiveness, cost and schedule implications, the effect on the system's technical quality/performance and the most suitable technique selected.

The following table will describe the identified risks, the significance of the risk and the contingency plan defined in relation to the answers to the questionnaires given by external stakeholders and the IEC PILOTING meeting held on December 1st, 2022 (see Section 2.1).

Table 4. PILOTING SoEL identified risks and evaluation.

Risk N°	Description	Probability	Impact	Risk response	Contingency Plan
Social Aspects: GDPR and others					
1	Not enough knowledge about the GDPR regulation from the inspection tasks operators	Medium	High	TRANSFER/ MITIGATE	The people in charge of planning and execute the inspection activities could not have a good knowledge about the GDPR. However, any inspection operator that starts to use PILOTING solution must have a minimum training on GPDR. This training will be included the GDPR requirements that apply to any PILOTING use case, identified during the PILOTING project and beyond. The GDPR is a regulation of obligatory compliance in all the European companies. Then, even if the I&M operators do not have a good knowledge of the regulation, they must sign a confidentiality agreement with their company, and its DPO will ensure that the compliance with the GDPR regulation.
2	Not enough confidence of the inspection operators in the new robotic inspection tools	Medium	High	MITIGATE	Work closely with the inspection operators to show that the results, after the inspections, are at least equivalent to the ones obtained by traditional inspection procedures. This aspect should also be considered as part of the industrialization and commercialization of the robotic systems, including training and certification to the inspection operators to use these new tools.
3	Capture data from non-involved people in the vicinity of the inspection activities	Medium	Medium	MITIGATE	The risk of non-involved people being in the vicinity of the inspection site is not very high. However, the operator should be aware of GPDR, and some minimal and continuous training is recommended.

					<p>In the refinery use case, no external personnel can enter in the facilities without authorizations. Just refinery staff could be in the vicinity of the inspection activities. However, it is important that GDPR regulation also applied to refinery staff not involved in the inspection.</p> <p>In the viaduct use case, they are infrastructures that are usually located in places that are difficult to access and where usually nobody is present.</p> <p>In tunnel use case, inside the tunnels there are not people present. But it is important to make sure that the images will not allow to recognize people inside their vehicles (in case the inspection is performed along with real traffic in one of the lanes).</p> <p>Then, as it was previously commented, it is important to train the inspectors that in case not-involved personnel are close to the inspection area, the inspection operation must comply with GDPR regulation.</p>
4	Insufficient security for personal data maintenance and storage	Low	High	AVOID	<p>Each company have its own procedure to the data retention/maintenance. Since PILOTING use cases are dealing with critical infrastructures, this is not only important to fulfil the GDPR, but also to guarantee that no sensible information, related to critical infrastructure is accessed by external actors with malicious purposes.</p> <p>Then, it is very important to make sure that only authorized</p>

					personnel will have access to the data collected.
5	Data processing agreement between the inspection operator and the data analytics service provider	Medium	High	AVOID	In case the data captured by the robotics vehicles is analysed by a different entity, it is important to make sure that a data processing agreement (that fulfils the GDPR) is in place.
Ethical Aspects: AI developments					
6	Changes of the future AI regulation that could affect PILOTING AI-based developments	Low	High	AVOID	The application of AI developments is really new, and its regulation is still under definition. Then, PILOTING AI algorithms developers are closely monitoring the 1 st guidelines of the European AI regulation in order to make sure that the PILOTING technological developments are not restricted by this regulation. However, and since PILOTING AI software performs inspection data analytics using advanced AI algorithms which will be focused only on the detection of infrastructures defects, we do not envisage important requirements to this software coming for the future AI regulation.
7	Use of the AI algorithms against the autonomy of the inspector operator	Low	High	MITIGATE	The "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI" defines that the AI developments must respect the autonomy of the human. In PILOTING, the AI algorithms will be used as guidelines, there are no plans to fully replace people for the final decision. The results will be always validated by an experience inspector.
8	Implications of the inspection regulations to highly	Low	High	MITIGATE	The current inspection regulation does not allow that an AI-based software decides fully autonomously (without an inspection operator) the

	automatic AI-based inspection analytics				identification and analysis of a defect. As just commented, in this project the AI algorithms will be used as guidelines, there are no plans to fully replace people for the final decision. The results will be always validated by an experience inspector.
9	Use of the AI algorithms, developed in PILOTING, for unacceptable purposes	Low	High	AVOID	AI algorithms in PILOTING are related to the detection of defects in infrastructure, so they are not targeting any sensible issue related to privacy or ethics, working in the minimal risk of the current European AI guidelines. The end-users will work with the final version of the algorithms and their use cannot be subliminal, manipulative, or exploitative and will not cause harm or remote biometric identification.
10	Use of the AI algorithms, developed in PILOTING, for high risks purposes	Low	High	AVOID	AI algorithms in PILOTING are related to the detection of defects in infrastructure, so they are not targeting any sensible issue related to privacy or ethics, working in the minimal risk category as defined in the current European AI guidelines. The end-users will work with the final version of the algorithms, and these do not include social creditworthiness evaluation systems, recruiting or employee-management systems, biometric identification in non-public spaces or systems used in administration of justice.
Legal aspects: Inspection regulation and insurance					
11	Fragmentation of the inspection regulation	High	Medium	ACCEPT	The regulation and guidelines that define the requirements for the inspection sector is very fragmented in Europe. Each country has a specific specification of the inspection requirements, and sometimes even they change depending on the asset owner. This will not

					change in the short term. However, we believe that the approach in PILOTING, with the development of the PILOTING I&M platform and services, will facilitate the adaptation of the technological solutions to the different requirements, making it more competitive than others.
12	Difficulty in obtaining insurance coverage for special inspection operations	Medium	High	MITIGATE	During the PILOTING experiments, this risk has not occurred. However, and from the experience of some industrial partners, this risk could be activated, especially when dealing with industrial inspection operations. The contingency plan is to agree liability compensation as part of the inspection contract.
Legal aspects: UAV regulation					
13	Not enough knowledge of the inspection managers about which UAS operations are possible and scalable within the current legal framework	High	High	MITIGATE	Specific training to inspector managers to know realistically which types of operations are possible and scalable with the current legal framework. Also, to be able to accurately estimate the effort and time to obtain the permits to flight.
14	Not enough knowledge within the company how to obtain the UAS permits before performing the	Medium	High	MITIGATE	If there is no department of the company that has experience or is in charge of managing the permit to flight, then it is desirable to subcontract the complete inspection service or an external expert or company that support how to manage and obtain the flight permits.

	inspection tasks				
15	Long times in obtaining the necessary flights permissions for the Specific category.	Medium	High	MITIGATE	From the experience in the PILOTING project, obtaining an operational authorization (flight permit) for the Specific category could require up to 6 months. This time should be considered when planning the inspections and also could affect the potential business exploitation of the technologies (specially for the refinery case where this type of authorization has been required).
16	UAV developed within the project will not be certified with the corresponding CE labelled.	Medium	High	ACCEPT	PILOTING UAVs will operate in open or specific category. By January 2024, this implies that they must be certified with a CE labelled (obtained through a conformity process with a homologated notified body) in order to be operated without requiring an operational authorization (which requires a long process as just commented). The PILOTING consortium is aware of this and, and this is why this aspect will be considered as part of the industrialization plan.
17	Still very difficult to obtain BVLOS flights	High	High	MITIGATE	The process to obtain BVLOS flight authorizations is still long, and it depends heavily on the surroundings of the area to be inspected (both at ground and aerial level), making more difficult the scalability of the inspections with aerial robots. This affects mainly to the viaduct use case since the refinery operations are mainly VLOS and in the tunnel the aeronautical drone regulation does not apply. Then, we propose in the first years of the future exploitation to focus on VLOS operations, and also make

					use of visual observers and the standard scenario (up to 2 km) to make the viaduct inspections more efficient in the short term.
18	Internal company requirements do not allow PILOTING UAVs to operate	Low	Medium	AVOID	PILOTING solution has been designed to comply with the European regulation and standards and taking into account the end-users' requirements. In fact, all PILOTING UAS operations have been performed fulfilling the current UAS legal framework. Moreover, all the PILOTING UAS have been operated in real industrial scenarios for three different end-users. Although, it is also true that end-users are treating PILOTING flights as experimental, and extra requirements may arise. Then, this risk will be considered in the development of the industrialization plan.
19	ATEX certification for UAVs	Medium	Medium	AVOID	The current use cases with UAVs in PILOTING are oriented to areas of the refinery where ATEX certification is not required. However, it could be necessary to be able to operate in ATEX areas for the future exploitation of the PILOTING solution. Then, PILOTING partners are working on the development of operational mitigations that may be useful to operate non-ATEX certified UAVs in ATEX zones in the future. In the long term, PILOTING partners should try to identify and support initiatives that are trying to adapt ATEX regulation to mobile systems (since it was designed for fixed equipment). For example, Sprint Robotics is working into this direction. Nevertheless, this modification could take more

					than 10 years due to the difficulties of the process and it is not a realistic contingency that could be used in the medium term.
Legal aspects: UGV regulation.					
20	Change of UGV regulation in the next years	Low	High	MITIGATE	Right now, there is not a specific operational requirements or regulation that applies to the use of unmanned ground robots which will be conducted in private properties. However, this could change, and it is important to continuously monitor the progress of UGV regulation.
21	Not enough knowledge within the company about UGVs regulation/guidelines before performing the inspection tasks	Medium	High	MITIGATE	As commented before, there is not a specific operational requirement to the use of unmanned ground robots which will be conducted in private properties. However, the use of UGVs for inspection tasks is growing and this situation may change. In order to perform these inspection tasks fulfilling the legal requirements it is desirable that the company has a department that is in charge of the checking the legal aspects with UGVs, or at least subcontract it to third party's experts.
22	Internal company requirements do not allow PILOTING UGVs to operate in the tunnel	Low	Medium	AVOID	During the development of the project several IEC meetings have been held, ensuring that the PILOTING solution is align with the internal requirements of the tunnel end-user. Furthermore, the UGV have been operated in a real tunnel with real traffic conditions.
23	ATEX certification of UGVs for the refinery	High	High	MITIGATE	The UGVs that we are developing in PILOTING are not intended to be ATEX certified. There are ATEX-certified UGVs on the market, but their cost is much higher. At PILOTING we are gaining

					<p>experience in the design of emergency procedures that could help us in the future to use non-ATEX UGVs in ATEX areas. However, this could be a limited factor for the future exploitation of the PILOTING ground robotic vehicles. Anyway, the developed autonomous navigation and manipulation technologies could be exploited if they are integrated in current ATEX-certified UGVs products. As previously commented, in the long-term PILOTING partners should try to identify and support initiatives that are trying to adapt ATEX regulation to mobile systems (since it was designed for fixed equipment). For example, Sprint Robotics is working into this direction. Nevertheless, this modification could take more than 10 years due to the difficulties of the process and it is not a realistic contingency that could be used in the medium term.</p>
--	--	--	--	--	--

2.4 Consultation of an external SoEL expert

As was introduced in the D9.3 (section 5.4), in order to set the SoEL requirements and potential SoEL risk of the technologies developed in PILOTING, a collaboration has been established with the H2020 project [Robotics4EU](#).

This collaboration has been set through different email and information exchange and follow-up meetings. Specifically, on 21st of September 2022, CATEC, as PILOTING coordinator, held a meeting with Robotics4EU project coordinator and personnel from the Laboratoire national de métrologie et d'essais (LNE)², entity in charge of the perform the maturity assessment model which is being developed within the project.

In this meeting, the Project Coordinator presented PILOTING project and main technologies, as well as what type of potential SoEL risks have been identified by the PILOTING consortium. LNE researchers analysed the information provided and give inputs about additional SoEL risks that from their experience should be considered as well. These inputs have been included in the results of the

² [LNE, Laboratoire national de métrologie et d'essais](#)

SoEL Impact Assessment presented in Table 4 (for example risk 11 was identified as result of this collaboration).

In addition, it is important to highlight that, from this initial collaboration, it has been proposed the study of one PILOTING technology during 2023 using the maturity assessment model that is being developed by Robotics4EU. Robotics4EU plans to finalize its maturity assessment model by the first quarter of 2023, so the timing fits well. This maturity assessment will be included as part of the industrialization plan (deliverable D10.7 “Preparation Plan for Commercialisation and Market Entry Future”). This collaboration will allow to perform a complete SoEL analysis according to the social, legal and ethical acceptance in the EU market.

3. Monitoring the correct execution of the project against the SoEL requirements

In addition to completing a 2nd Impact assessment report, more focused on the point of view of the future exploitation of the PILOTING results, this report includes an analysis of how the results of the 1st Impact assessment report (D9.2), more focused on test the compliance with the SoEL requirements during the development of the PILOTING R&D project, are being implemented and monitored.

Furthermore, this report summarizes how the "Guidelines for the impact assessment which applies to each PILOTING Impact Scenario" defined in the deliverable D9.1 and D9.3 are being complied within PILOTING, in order to have a better understanding about how PILOTING developments are aligned with the SoEL requirements among different type of pilots and their geographical/legal implications.

3.1 Monitoring that the results of the 1st PILOTING impact assessment (D9.2) are being implemented

The aim of this section is to show how the PILOTING consortium monitors that the results of the 1st “Impact assessment report” (D9.2) are implemented by all relevant partners as the system is integrated, tested and evaluated in the pilot experiments. To this end, the strategy followed has been the continuous analysis of the SoEL risk matrix, the result of the D9.2 through:

- Presentation and discussion during the project's General Meetings (GM). The SoEL risk matrix has been presented in the WP9 Presentation of the GM from its elaboration (M12). In these meetings, the partners involved in each PILOTING SoEL risk have been questioned to see how they are implementing the contingency plan defined, and the qualification of the probability and impact has also been analysed.
- Periodic e-mails for PILOTING partners to remind them to analyse their developments from an SoEL point of view and add any comments to the SoEL monitoring document available in basecamp: <https://3.basecamp.com/4387818/buckets/14975764/vaults/5351999051>

Table 5 and Table 6 show the updates D9.1 SoEL risk matrix, taking into account the work performed through the monitoring completed during this period (M12-M36).

Table 5. Management risks identified in the 1st Impact Assessment Report (D9.2) – Update.

Risk N°	Description	Probability	Impact	Risk response	Contingency Plan	Monitoring during the project's cycle life
1	Missing or inadequate legal requirements of GDPR for data processing during the project's life cycle	Low	High	MITIGATE	<p>Informed consent procedures have been defined and implemented. Only authorized personnel will have access to the data collected in project management activities. If sensitive data are collected, these will be preserved in an anonymized and aggregated way and deleted after the project end. Finally, PILOTING project has appointed a Data Project Officer (Inmaculada Huertas Olivares) who can answer any question regarding the GDPR fulfilment.</p>	<p>Informed consent procedures have been implemented whenever necessary.</p> <p>The following is a description of the activities organized within PILOTING, and how the informed consent procedures have been implemented for each of them:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PILOTING User Group: In the context of the PILOTING project, a PILOTING User Group has been organized to obtain feedback from a large set of external entities and stakeholders from the I&M community. Some data, like the name, surname, e-mail, entity or work position, has been collected and recorded. These data remain secure and will be accessible only by authorized personnel with special permission upon request in the internal server related to the project. Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties. Nevertheless, in the PILOTING invitation e-mail, a specific clause for accomplishing GDPR requirements is included (see Figure 2).

						<p>Privacy Notice</p> <p>The actual personal details of the participating members of PILOTING User Group that will be kept by the project are name, surname, affiliation, expertise and email address. These details will be kept for the purposes of PILOTING research and only while kept only throughout the project duration (until 31/12/2023). Any dissemination of these details will be done internally to PILOTING project. Any other usage will be notified to members per case. These data will be stored to the dedicated internal PILOTING server (PILOTING consortium access), while each member will have the right to be removed from this list at any time (with an email to piloting-project@cattec.aero). With the acceptance in participating to this user-group, each member accepts the above policy in data purpose, duration, access and right to be forgotten (as policies of GDPR).</p> <p>Figure 2. Privacy Notice include in the PILOTING User Group invitation e-mail.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Organization of workshops:</u> Due to the travel restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, all the PILOTING workshops organized within the project have been online. For these activities, some personal data, like name, surname, e-mail, entity, or work position, has been collected to confirm attendance at the activity but none of these data have been recorded. In addition, participants had to accept the privacy terms that must be selected within web forms. The only data collected were during the "PILOTING Innovation workshops", where participants were asked to vote for the more
--	--	--	--	--	--	---

						<p>promising PILOTING technologies. The answers given to the surveys/questionnaires have been recorded for reporting purposes only, and it will not be possible to identify the author of each response. The recorded data will not include any personal identification. Furthermore, the activity's objectives have been communicated through e-mail, registration sheet, etc. As an example, you can see the registration form for the second PILOTING workshop in this link.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• <u>PILOTING Demonstrations:</u> In the project framework, large-scale demonstrations are being organized in each PILOTING scenario. These demos will include external participants from the full PILOTING value chain (from technological providers to inspection service providers and asset owners), ensuring the future industrial application and exploitation of PILOTING technological developments. In these events only data may be collected from participants in the form of promotional images/videos, which will be used for the dissemination of the project. In these cases, the external participants have been duly informed through the PILOTING Information sheet and have signed the Informed Consent Form (see deliverable D1.1). Some examples have been included in the Annex I, after obtaining the
--	--	--	--	--	--	--

						people's permission (due to a public deliverable). The rest of the Informed Consent Forms is available on internal CATEC repositories, which only authorized personnel can access under permission.
2	Missing or inadequate legal requirements of GDPR for data processing after the project's life cycle	Medium	High	TRANSFER/ MITIGATE	The information obtained from project management activities like surveys/workshops will be used to make project reports / analyse the feedback from the I&M community or make publications in scientific journals. These results do not make it possible to identify the source of information. About the recorded data, only authorized personnel will be able the access and these will be	As mentioned above, recording personal data from external participants has not been necessary for most of the PILOTING activities. The only exceptions have been the following <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To confirm the PILOTING User Group, data, like name, surname, e-mail, entity, or work position, have been recorded. Only authorized personnel will be able the access and these will be deleted after the end of the project. • In some project activities, like demos or workshops, some pictures or videos might be recorded for dissemination purposes. In this case, the Inform Consent Form has been shared and signed (see an example in Annex I: Informed consent form (examples)). This form is being shared after obtaining the people's permission through an email (due to a public deliverable, see an example of this email in the Figure 2). The rest of the Informed Consent Form is available on internal CATEC repositories, which only authorized personnel can access under permission.

					<p>deleted after the end of the project. Once the project has been completed, the data controller will continue to be responsible for treating this risk. Finally, PILOTING project has appointed a Data Project Officer (Inmaculada Huertas Olivares) who can answer any question regarding the GDPR fulfilment.</p>	<div data-bbox="1323 229 2007 616" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p>Dear "PILOTING 1st large demonstration in viaduct scenario" attendant,</p> <p>You are receiving this email since you have participated in "PILOTING 1st large demonstration in viaduct scenario" (https://piloting-project.eu).</p> <p>The actual personal data that we manage are regulated by the Informed consent form, signed during the event (please, find it attached). However, we are writing to you because we would like to share this document in a PILOTING public deliverable to report objectives. This form contains info like the name and the signature. You will have the right to be removed from this list at any time (with an email to piloting-project@catec.aero).</p> <p>Please, could you give us your acceptance answering this email. With your acceptance, you accept the above policy in data purpose, duration, access and right to be forgotten (as policies of GDPR).</p> <p>Best regards, PILOTING Project Coordinator.</p> </div> <p>Figure 3. Example of email to include the Informed consent form in this deliverable.</p>
3	Inefficient communication channels to obtain SoEL feedback from stakeholders	Low	Medium	MITIGATE	<p>Four different channels have been established to obtain stakeholder's feedback. In case of an inadequate communication with the stakeholders through these channels,</p>	<p>Until now, a good communication with the stakeholders has been performed through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PILOTING User Group. • Participation in I&M events: workshops, conferences, events, etc. • Organization of workshops. • Pilot demonstrations. <p>In addition, the piloting-project@catec.aero e-mail address is kept available for interested parties to send any questions regarding the project. All e-mails sent from this address include the Privacy Notice.</p>

					PILOTING project has made available the following e-mail to send any request or complaint: piloting-project@catec.aero .	
4	Insufficient information for data subjects	Medium	High	MITIGATE	PILOTING project provides a specific e-mail (piloting-project@catec.aero) to solve any concerns related to personal data recruitment and treatment.	PILOTING consortiums specify a Privacy Notice in all its communications with stakeholders. In addition, the e-mail address piloting-project@catec.aero e-mail is kept available for the data subjects, in case they wish to withdraw the rights granted in the Inform consent forms.
5	Insufficient security for personal data maintenance and storage	Low	High	AVOID (measures already taken)	As it was described in the D1.2, POPD - Requirement N°2, personal data will be recorded in the internal server during the cycle life of the project. Only authorized personnel will be access to this information.	Any personal data recorded within the project will be saved in the internal project repository: Basecamp (https://3.basecamp.com/4387818/projects/14975764). This repository complies with GDPR. Only authorized personnel, with special permission upon request, will be access to this information, just to the project purposes. Finally, any personal data recorded will be deleted after the project end.

6	Withdrawal of a partner and lose control of the previous data collected	Low	High	TRANSFER	This situation is regulated based on the PILOTING consortium's Grant Agreement.	<p>HONEYWELL stopped its project's participation after the first year of the project (2020).</p> <p>Access to the repository by HONEYWELL staff was removed, and they no longer have access to the PILOTING developments/data collected in the project framework.</p> <p>In addition, the situation has been regulated following the basis of the consortium's Grant Agreement. An amendment to regulate this issue has been signed and approved by the EC.</p>
---	---	-----	------	----------	---	---

Table 6. Technical risks identified in the 1st Impact Assessment Report (D9.2) – Update.

Risk N°	Description	Probability	Impact	Risk response	Contingency Plan	Monitoring during the project's cycle life
Data protection						
7	Incidental personal data collection during the use cases	Low	High	MITIGATE	The risk of collecting incidental personal data from 3rd parties has been minimized. However, during the use cases, there are possibilities that natural persons can be captured on video/image,	<p>Any personal data have been collected or recorded during the PILOTING flight experiments until now.</p> <p>The data collected and processed are focused on infrastructure defects.</p> <p>If this could happen in the future, informed consent processes would be applied.</p>

					<p>although there is no intention to identify persons from the data.</p> <p>In this case, the image collected will be modified or deleted so that the person cannot be identified. If this is not possible, the defined informed consent procedures will be followed.</p>	
8	<p>Sensitive data is processed.</p> <p>Sensors might capture sensitive data.</p>	Low	High	<p>AVOID (measures already taken)</p>	<p>The system has been designed to not collect any data that would be considered sensitive personal data.</p>	<p>As was introduced in the deliverable D9.3 (section 4.1, Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects), an analysis of the type of data capture from the PILOTING robot's on-board sensors have been completed.</p> <p>These sensors are focused on the inspection and the infrastructures defects. Then, the camera will only record the images indicated by the operator/inspector, which will only be focused on the defects to be analysed.</p>
9	<p>Missing or inadequate legal requirements of GDPR for data processing during the project's life cycle</p>	Low	High	<p>MITIGATE</p>	<p>See Table 5, Risk 1.</p>	<p>See Table 5, Risk 1.</p>

10	Missing or inadequate legal requirements of GDPR for data processing after the project's life cycle	Medium	High	TRANSFER/ MITIGATE	See Table 5, Risk 2.	See Table 5, Risk 2.
11	Insufficient information for data subjects	Medium	High	MITIGATE	See Table 5, Risk 4.	See Table 5, Risk 4.
12	Insufficient security for personal data maintenance and storage	Low	High	AVOID (measures already taken)	See Table 5, Risk 5.	See Table 5, Risk 5.
Operation of Unmanned Vehicles						
13	ATEX certification for UAVs	Medium	Medium	AVOID	The current use cases with UAVs are oriented to areas of the refinery where ATEX certification is not required. Also, PILOTING partners are working to develop operational mitigations that may be useful to	The first PILOTING refinery demonstration occurred in September 2022 (from 12th to 16th) in the CHEVRON Oronite Plant (Gonfreville, France). In these demonstrations, the following UAVs were tested: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AEROX: In-line inspection of storage tanks. • HYBRID: Refinery water handling pipes inspection. • AEROCAM: In-line inspection of storage tanks. Decom Zone Inspection – Navigation, Stairs, Manipulation and Pressure Vessel. These demonstrations were organized in areas of the refinery where no ATEX certification it is required.

					operate non-ATEX UAVs in ATEX zones in the future.	
13	ATEX certification for UGVs	Medium	Medium	AVOID	The current use cases with UGVs are oriented to areas of the refinery where ATEX certification is not required. Also, PILOTING partners are working to develop operational mitigations that may be useful to operate non-ATEX UGVs in ATEX zones in the future.	<p>The only PILOTING refinery demonstration occurred in September 2022 (from 12th to 16th) in the CHEVRON Oronite Plant (Gonfreville, France). In these demonstrations, the following UGVs were tested:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RISING. • ETHZ-UGV. <p>These demonstrations were organized in areas of the refinery where no ATEX certification it is required.</p>
14	Certification of UGVs	Medium	High	AVOID	The use cases involve the use of UGVs in areas that are not open to regular traffic on open and public roads. This fact can facilitate the use of UGVs in the future.	<p>During this time, PILOTING UGV developments have been tested in the following real scenarios:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Refinery Scenario</u>. The first PILOTING refinery demonstration occurred in September 2022 (from 12th to 16th) in the CHEVRON Oronite Plant (Gonfreville, France). In these demonstrations, the following UGVs were tested: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ RISING. ○ ETHZ-UGV.

						<p>The refinery is a private property, not open to regular traffic. In addition, the work areas were closed to external's project personnel during the project's demonstration. Then, no specific operational requirements are needed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Tunnel Scenario</u>. The 1st high-value campaign in the tunnel scenario took place in September-October (from 30th -8st), in different tunnel uses cases in Metsovo (Greece). In particular <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Drainage tunnel scenario, where CART UGV and TT-DRONE were tested. ○ Road tunnel, where CART was tested in different validation tests. <p>In the drainage tunnel, the traffic was not open to the regular traffic. In the road tunnel, the left lane was closed (to perform the experiments) whereas the right lane was open to the regular traffic. However, safety measures were implemented. The lane where the experiments took place was close, and safety personnel with flags and safety cars of Egnatia Motorway were used. The experiments took place with good vision conditions in order to increase the safety. Apart of the regular traffic, it was not allowed that people external to the project were present. Only consortium members/partners.</p>
15	Safety risks affecting crawler	Medium	High	MITIGATE	Latest safety standards related to robotics vehicles are taken into	Machinery 2006/42/EG or Low Voltage (LVD) 2014/35/EU directive is applicable for safety. Along with directives for electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) 2014/30/EU, Restriction of Hazardous Substance (RoHS)

	design and operation				consideration in the design and development of the crawler system and operational concept.	2011/65/EU and Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) 2012/19/EU directives. Harmonized standards are applied by partners in the design of the crawler for compliance of conformity with these directives. Among other requirements the Machinery and LVD stipulates that a manufacturer must carry out a risk assessment regarding safety and accident risks for people. An additional risk assessment is created by or in conjunction with the test site owners to account for hazards associated with environment in which the machine is used and combined hazards.
Artificial Intelligence						
16	Regulation related to AI algorithms is mandatory in the future	Medium	Low	AVOID	AI algorithms in PILOTING are related to the detection of defects in infrastructure, so they are not targeting any sensible issue related to privacy or ethics. Anyway, during PILOTING project, new developments on a future AI regulation will be closely monitored	<p>Artificial intelligence algorithms have been developed to automatically detect defects in infrastructures.</p> <p>Also, deep convolutional neuronal networks have been implemented and trained to detect such defects.</p> <p>These algorithms have only been trained on images showing infrastructure defects, with no people present.</p> <p>In addition, during this period, PILOTING consortium has been monitoring any update in the AI regulation, to align its development with the principles established by the EC. In the D9.3, the last updates in this regulation have been included.</p>

17	AI algorithms applied to inspection are required to be certified	Medium	Medium	AVOID	<p>An experienced inspector always validates AI algorithms results. In the future, and after the AI algorithms are validated for an extensive period of time if the system is planned to be used without any supervision, it is expected that some type of certification will be required.</p>	<p>Until now, the PILOTING consortium has been working on developing AI algorithms complying with the SoEL requirements.</p> <p>These algorithms just have been tested on the framework of the project, with the supervision of the PILOTING technical partners and experts on the inspection procedures.</p> <p>The PILOTING consortium will continue monitoring if some certification could be required in the future.</p>
----	--	--------	--------	-------	--	--

3.2 How PILOTING complies with SoEL requirements

Based on the Impact Assessment performed in Section 2, this section summarizes how the "PILOTING Impact Scenarios" comply with each SoEL requirement defined in the D9.3, Section 4 - Guidelines for the impact assessment.

Table 7 reminds us of which of the defined SoEL requirements and principles apply to each impact scenario.

Table 7. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Scenario.

Impact Scenarios	Social	Ethical	Legal
Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	UAV regulation ATEX requirements
Impact Scenario 2: Refinery - Crawler	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	ATEX requirements
Impact Scenario 3: Refinery-UGV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	ATEX requirements UGV standards and recommendations covered in the ISO 3691-4:2020
Impact Scenario 4: Bridge/Viaduct - UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	UAV regulation
Impact Scenario 5: Tunnel – UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	-
Impact Scenario 6: Tunnel - UGV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	UGV Regulation: Standard for automated guided vehicles

Next, each of the SoEL requirements are analysed for the different Impact scenarios:

➤ **Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV**

Social	Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects", the only way in which external data can be collected from external participants is through the data captured from the on-board sensors.
---------------	---

In this impact scenario, the following robots and on-board sensors are being used:

PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar
AEROX	X	X		
HYBRID	X	X		X

- **Operational Camara.** This type of sensor can collect images. However, only images of the infrastructure, previously indicated by the operator/inspector, will be recorded. Then, any personal data would be collected even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place.
- **Situational awareness camera.** This type of sensor can collect images, but the image will be focused on the drone components/infrastructure and will not record any type of personal data.
- **LIDAR** (Light Detection and Ranging): the LIDAR sensor generates a point cloud that allows objects to be identified. However, if a person is detected, it will not be possible to distinguish any personal data (sex, race, etc.), because this sensor's cloud point does not have enough resolution. In addition, only data from the infrastructure will be analysed and processed.

In addition, it is important to highlight that during the pilot experiments, the scenarios will be restricted, and no external personnel are expected to enter the area during the missions. Then, it is not expected to collect personal data during the project's technical activities or even in future exploitation activities using PILOTING technologies. However, if personal data are collected, the GDPR must be applied by the entity in charge of the operation.

Ethical

Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Ethical Aspects", the main applicable regulatory framework is related to AI technologies, summarized in the "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI" and in the "AI ACT" proposed by the EC.

In the PILOTING project, algorithms are focused only on the detection of infrastructure defects and comply with all the ethical principles defined by the EC:

- **Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI:** Respect for human autonomy; Prevention of harm; Fairness and Explicability.
- **AI ACT:** The category that best fits the purpose of the PILOTING Project belongs to "Limited and minimal risk AI Systems" and can be related to "Most other AI systems" since there is no specific field of application defined for I&M or autonomous navigation use of Artificial Intelligence.

Then, as conclusion, within PILOTING, an AI system for inspection analytics, which will be integrated in all the PILOTING robotic solutions and impact scenarios, is being developed. This AI software performs inspection data analytics using advanced AI algorithms. These algorithms will be focused only on the

	detection of infrastructures defects. Then, this AI software will comply with all the ethical principles defined by the EC.
<u>Legal</u>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspects", regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the operation of Unmanned Vehicles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UAV: PILOTING Project experiments comply with European Drone Regulation. The Specific category applies to the Refinery UAV inspection use cases, since the refinery in France is in a no-fly zone (due to the criticality of the infrastructure) and only operations under the Specific category are allowed. Operational authorization has been obtained from the national aviation authority to perform the pilot demonstrations. <p>Finally, concerning with the operation in Oil&Gas environments, due to the difficulty of apply ATEX certification to robotics solutions, PILOTING experiments have been performed in non-ATEX areas. Moreover, emergency operational procedures are being designed following the CHEVRON guidelines "Guidance Notes for Inspection using Unmanned Aircraft Systems".</p>

➤ **Impact Scenario 2: Refinery -Crawler**

<u>Social</u>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects", the only way in which external data can be collected from external participants is through the data captured from the on-board sensors.</p> <p>In this impact scenario, the following robots and on-board sensors are being used:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="368 1220 1425 1464"> <thead> <tr> <th>PILOTING Robotic Vehicles</th> <th>Operational Camera</th> <th>Situational awareness camera</th> <th>Infrared Camera</th> <th>Lidar</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>BIKE</td> <td>X</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>X</td> </tr> <tr> <td>HYBRID</td> <td>X</td> <td>X</td> <td></td> <td>X</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational Camara. This type of sensor can collect images. However, only images of the infrastructure, previously indicated by the operator/inspector, will be recorded. Then, any personal data would be collected even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place. • Situational awareness camera. This type of sensor can collect images, but the image will be focused on the drone components/infrastructure and will not record any type of data. • LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging): the LIDAR sensor generates a point cloud that allows objects to be identified. However, if a person is detected, it will not be possible to distinguish any personal data (sex, race, etc.), because this sensor's cloud point does not have enough resolution. In addition, only data from the infrastructure will be analysed and processed. 	PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar	BIKE	X			X	HYBRID	X	X		X
PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar												
BIKE	X			X												
HYBRID	X	X		X												

	In addition, it is important to highlight that during the pilot experiments, the scenarios will be restricted, and no external personnel are expected to enter the area during the missions. Then, it is not expected to collect personal data during the project's technical activities or even in future exploitation activities using PILOTING technologies. However, if personal data are collected, the GDPR must be applied by the company in charge.
<u>Ethical</u>	The same analysis applies as in “Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV”.
<u>Legal</u>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspects", regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the operation of Unmanned Vehicles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UAV: PILOTING Project experiments comply with European Drone Regulation. The Specific category applies to the Refinery UAV inspection use cases, since the refinery in France is in a no-fly zone (due to the criticality of the infrastructure) and only operations under the Specific category are allowed. Operational authorization has been obtained from the national aviation authority to perform the pilot demonstrations. <p>Finally, concerning with the operation in Oil&Gas environments, due to the difficulty of apply ATEX certification to robotics solutions, PILOTING experiments have been performed in non-ATEX areas. Moreover, emergency operational procedures are being designed following the CHEVRON guidelines “Guidance Notes for Inspection using Unmanned Aircraft Systems”.</p>

➤ **Impact Scenario 3: Refinery- UGV**

<u>Social</u>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects", the only way in which external data can be collected from external participants is through the data captured from the on-board sensors.</p> <p>In this impact scenario, the following robots and on-board sensors are being used:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="368 1467 1425 1713"> <thead> <tr> <th>PILOTING Robotic Vehicles</th> <th>Operational Camera</th> <th>Situational awareness camera</th> <th>Infrared Camera</th> <th>Lidar</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>RISING</td> <td>X</td> <td></td> <td>X</td> <td>X</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UGV</td> <td>X</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>X</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational Camara. This type of sensor can collect images. However, only images of the infrastructure, previously indicated by the operator/inspector, will be recorded. Then, any personal data would be collected even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place. • Infrared Camera (IR): The Infrared Camera uses infrared energy for the detection and measurement of objects. They can also detect invisible 	PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar	RISING	X		X	X	UGV	X			X
PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar												
RISING	X		X	X												
UGV	X			X												

	<p>infrared wavelengths, enabling the camera to see in the dark. Only data from infrastructure will be analysed and processed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging): the LIDAR sensor generates a point cloud that allows objects to be identified. However, if a person is detected, it will not be possible to distinguish any personal data (sex, race, etc.), because this sensor's cloud point does not have enough resolution. In addition, only data from the infrastructure will be analysed and processed. <p>In addition, it is important to highlight that during the pilot experiments, the scenarios will be restricted, and no external personnel are expected to enter the area during the missions. Then, it is not expected to collect personal data during the project's technical activities or even in future exploitation activities using PILOTING technologies. However, if personal data are collected, the GDPR must be applied by the company in charge.</p>
<p><u>Ethical</u></p>	<p>The same analysis applies as in “Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV”.</p>
<p><u>Legal</u></p>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspects", regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the operation of Unmanned Vehicles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UGV: The refinery is private property, not open to regular traffic, so no specific operational requirements are needed. In addition, the work areas were closed to external's project personnel during the project's demonstration. Anyway, the design of the system has been based on UGV standards and recommendations covered in the ISO 3691-4:2020 to facilitate future exploitation. <p>Finally, concerning with the operation in Oil&Gas environments, due to the difficulty of apply ATEX certification to robotics solutions, PILOTING experiments have been performed in non-ATEX areas.</p>

➤ **Impact Scenario 4: Bridges/Viaducts – UAV**

<p><u>Social</u></p>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects", the only way in which external data can be collected from external participants is through the data captured from the on-board sensors.</p> <p>In this impact scenario, the following robots and on-board sensors are being used:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="370 1653 1425 1899"> <thead> <tr> <th>PILOTING Robotic Vehicles</th> <th>Operational Camera</th> <th>Situational awareness camera</th> <th>Infrared Camera</th> <th>Lidar</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AERO-CAM</td> <td>X</td> <td>X</td> <td></td> <td>X</td> </tr> <tr> <td>VIAD-DRONE</td> <td>X</td> <td>X</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational Camara. This type of sensor can collect images. However, only images of the infrastructure, previously indicated by the 	PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar	AERO-CAM	X	X		X	VIAD-DRONE	X	X		
PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar												
AERO-CAM	X	X		X												
VIAD-DRONE	X	X														

	<p>operator/inspector, will be recorded. Then, any personal data would be collected even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Situational awareness camera. This type of sensor can collect images, but the image will be focused on the drone components/infrastructure and will not record any type of data. • LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging): the LIDAR sensor generates a point cloud that allows objects to be identified. However, if a person is detected, it will not be possible to distinguish any personal data (sex, race, etc.), because this sensor's cloud point does not have enough resolution. In addition, only data from the infrastructure will be analysed and processed. <p>In addition, it is important to highlight that during the pilot experiments, the scenarios will be restricted, and no external personnel are expected to enter the area during the missions. Then, it is not expected to collect personal data during the project's technical activities or even in future exploitation activities using PILOTING technologies. However, if personal data are collected, the GDPR must be applied by the company in charge.</p>
<p><u>Ethical</u></p>	<p>The same analysis applies as in “Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV”.</p>
<p><u>Legal</u></p>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspects", regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the operation of Unmanned Vehicles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UAV: The UAS operating in the Bridges/Viaducts scenario can operate on the Open or Specific category depending on whether the operation is performed under VLOS or BVLOS rules. Due to the nature of PILOTING inspections and their location, when the UAS has operated in Open Category, the subcategory A3 applied, operating in a private built and it not being necessary to ask for authorization. When the UAS will operate in specific category, an operational authorization will be required to the national aviation authority to perform the pilot demonstrations.

➤ **Impact Scenario 5: Tunnel – UAV**

<p><u>Social</u></p>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects", the only way in which external data can be collected from external participants is through the data captured from the on-board sensors.</p> <p>In this impact scenario, the following robots and on-board sensors are being used:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="368 1794 1426 1982"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="368 1794 624 1928">PILOTING Robotic Vehicles</th> <th data-bbox="624 1794 823 1928">Operational Camera</th> <th data-bbox="823 1794 1050 1928">Situational awareness camera</th> <th data-bbox="1050 1794 1251 1928">Infrared Camera</th> <th data-bbox="1251 1794 1426 1928">Lidar</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="368 1928 624 1982">TT-DRONE</td> <td data-bbox="624 1928 823 1982">X</td> <td data-bbox="823 1928 1050 1982"></td> <td data-bbox="1050 1928 1251 1982"></td> <td data-bbox="1251 1928 1426 1982"></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>					PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar	TT-DRONE	X			
PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar											
TT-DRONE	X														

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational Camara. This type of sensor can collect images. However, only images of the infrastructure, previously indicated by the operator/inspector, will be recorded. Then, any personal data would be collected even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place. <p>In addition, it is important to highlight that during the pilot experiments, the scenarios will be restricted, and no external personnel are expected to enter the area during the missions. Then, it is not expected to collect personal data during the project's technical activities or even in future exploitation activities using PILOTING technologies. However, if personal data are collected, the GDPR must be applied by the company in charge.</p>
<u>Ethical</u>	The same analysis applies as in “Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV”.
<u>Legal</u>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspects", regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the operation of Unmanned Vehicles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>UAV:</u> The European Drone Regulation does not apply to indoor operations. Then, it does not apply to the tunnel scenario with the TT-DRONE.

➤ **Impact Scenario 6: Tunnel -UGV**

<u>Social</u>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects", the only way in which external data can be collected from external participants is through the data captured from the on-board sensors.</p> <p>In this impact scenario, the following robots and on-board sensors are being used:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="368 1350 1425 1541"> <thead> <tr> <th>PILOTING Robotic Vehicles</th> <th>Operational Camera</th> <th>Situational awareness camera</th> <th>Infrared Camera</th> <th>Lidar</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>CART</td> <td>X</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>X</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational Camara. This type of sensor can collect images. However, only images of the infrastructure, previously indicated by the operator/inspector, will be recorded. Then, any personal data would be collected even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place. • LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging): the LIDAR sensor generates a point cloud that allows objects to be identified. However, if a person is detected, it will not be possible to distinguish any personal data (sex, race, etc.), because this sensor's cloud point does not have enough resolution. In addition, only data from the infrastructure will be analysed and processed. 	PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar	CART	X			X
PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar							
CART	X			X							

	In addition, it is important to highlight that during the pilot experiments, the scenarios will be restricted, and no external personnel are expected to enter the area during the missions. Then, it is not expected to collect personal data during the project's technical activities or even in future exploitation activities using PILOTING technologies. However, if personal data are collected, the GDPR must be applied by the company in charge.
<u>Ethical</u>	The same analysis applies as in “Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV”.
<u>Legal</u>	<p>Following the "Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspects", regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the operation of Unmanned Vehicles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>UGV</u>: The framework of PILOTING Project is conducted in a close lane without traffic, so no specific authorizations are needed. Anyway, the design of the system has been based on UGV standards for automated guided vehicles to facilitate future exploitation.

4. Conclusions

This deliverable integrates the results of the 2nd impact assessment against the different SoEL requirements defined in the D9.3 "Principles for impact assessment of PILOTING against SoEL requirements" and focused on the future exploitation of PILOTING technologies.

A total of 23 risks have been identified and treated as results of the SoEL impact assessment. From all these risks and contingency plans, the following major recommendations that could support the future commercial use of the PILOTING technologies have been identified:

- Provide specific training about GPDR aspect to inspection operators in order to better understand when their inspection operations with robotic vehicles cannot fulfil any GPDR regulatory aspect.
- Include an AI ethical assessment when any AI-based algorithms is used as part of an inspection procedure, even in case of using third party developed SW.
- Train the inspection managers in UAS regulation in order to understand which types of operations with UAS can scale well, and also the process and time required to obtain the flight authorizations for the different UAS operations.
- For certain types of operations with UAS, it will be required that the UAVs obtain a CE label after a conformity process with a notified body. This process must be considered as part of the industrialization plan of certain PILOTING technologies.
- Currently, there is no specific regulation on UGVs. Although this may be seen as an advantage as a first step, it is also true that this situation may change, and it may happen that the investments on certain UGVs products cannot be used any longer due to not fulfilment of regulatory requirements. This risk should be considered in future exploitation and industrialization plans.

- ATEX certification is an important limited factor in the petrochemical sector. For UGVs, and since there are already ATEX-certified products in the market, it is recommended to incorporate PILOTING technologies in these products. For UAVs, it is not foreseen that aerial systems can be ATEX certified. Then, and in order to maximize the exploitation of these technologies, it is important to develop operational mitigations acceptable by the end-users.

Finally, it has been also checked and justified that all the SoEL risks identified in D9.2 (related to the R&D project execution and the pilot experiments) have been managed correctly, being able to correctly manage all the identified SoEL aspects during the execution of PILOTING project.

Annex I: Informed consent form (examples)

H2020-ICT-2018-2020		
INFORMED CONSENT FORM		
Project Acronym	PILOTING	
Project Name	PILOTS for robotic and Inspection and maintenance Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and prototype applications	
Grant Agreement n°	871542	
Start date of the project	01/01/2020	
End date of the project	31/12/2023	
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871542		
CONTACT DETAILS: piloting-project@catec.aero		
DATE: 26/07/2022		
<u>WHAT WILL I BE ASKED TO DO?</u>		
<p>You will be asked to participate in the "1st large-scale PILOTING demonstration" within the framework of the PILOTING Project. One of the main milestones within the project is to complete a large-scale demonstration of the technologies developed in the three scenarios: refineries, viaduct/bridges and tunnels. This event represents the 1st large-scale demonstration in the viaduct scenario.</p>		
<p>The demonstration is intended to comply with the agenda schedule chronologically. Participation is voluntary. You are under no pressure to participate if you don't wish. You are free not to occupy yourself on matters that you do not wish. All the necessary precautions will be taken to protect your anonymity and confidentiality. If you wish to withdraw from the workshop, any information collected to that point will be destroyed if you do not wish of us to use them.</p>		
<u>TYPE OF INFORMATION THAT WILL BE COLLECTED</u>		
<p>In this demonstration, images and videos could be taken and filmed to disseminate PILOTING project activities. This is the only data that will be kept due to the purpose of the project communication. Even with your permission, we will not refer to you or quote you in any publication without allowing you to verify the accuracy of quotes being used.</p>		

H2020-ICT-2018-2020

Personal data like name, surname, email address or work position will not be collected for project objectives.

If you want your personal data to be removed from the multimedia content published in the project communication channels, please send us an email to: piloting-Project@catec.aero

CAN WE CONTACT YOU FOR FURTHER RESEARCH?

You may contact me in the future for further research related to the PILOTING project:
Yes No

CONFIRMATION

Your participation in this study is only possible if you freely and independently sign this consent to authorize us to use the data you provide. If you do not wish to do so, please do not participate in this study.

Your signature on this form indicates that you:

- Are 18 years or older and am competent to provide consent
- Have read and understood the information about the project, as provided in the PILOTING Information Sheet.
- Voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- Understand that even if you agree to participate now, you can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
- Understand that all information you provide will be treated confidentially.
- Understand that in any report on the results of this research your identity will remain anonymous
- Understand that if you inform the researcher that you or someone else is at risk of harm they may have to report this to the relevant authorities - they will discuss this with you first but may be required to report with or without your permission.
- Understand that signed consent forms will be retained until the end of the project
- Understand that under freedom of information legalization you are entitled to access the information you have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
- Understand that you are free to contact any of the people involved in the research, through the contact details provided in the bottom of the form, to seek further clarification and information.

H2020-ICT-2018-2020

Participant's name:
Inés Azpeitia González

Participant's Signature:

Date:
26th July, 2022

Researcher's Name:
MARÍA JOSÉ PEÑA MANRIQUE

Researcher's Signature:

Date:
26th July, 2022

QUESTION/CONCERNS

If you have any further questions or want clarification regarding this research and/or your participation, please contact

Thank you for your collaboration!

H2020-ICT-2018-2020

Participant's name:
JOSE IGNACIO JARDI CUERDA

Participant's Signature:

Date:
26th July, 2022

Researcher's Name:
MARIA JOSÉ PEÑA MANRIQUE

Researcher's Signature:

Date:
26th July, 2022

QUESTION/CONCERNS

If you have any further questions or want clarification regarding this research and/or your participation, please contact

Thank you for your collaboration!